

Citizen Science boosted Brazilian ornithology, but what about the future?

A Ciência Cidadã impulsionou a ornitologia brasileira, mas e o futuro?

Manuscript published at Boletim da Sociedade Brasileira de Ornitologia, 10(34):2-8, June 2024.

English version by River Warbler Ahlquist¹ and Eduardo R. Alexandrino²

1 - Undergraduate student, Cornell University. Granted by – Experimental Learning Award – summer 2024.

2 - Post-doctoral fellow, Cornell Lab of Ornithology (Cornell University, USA).

How to cite this document:

Ahlquist RW and Alexandrino ER. 2024. Citizen Science boosted Brazilian ornithology, but what about the future? Manuscript translation from Alexandrino ER. 2024. A Ciência Cidadã impulsionou a ornitologia brasileira, mas e o futuro? Boletim da Sociedade Brasileira de Ornitologia, 10(34):2-8. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12690829>

Citizen Science boosted Brazilian ornithology, but what about the future?

Eduardo R. Alexandrino^{1,2}

1- Cornell Lab of Ornithology, Ithaca, NY, 14850, USA.

2 - Universidade de São Paulo, Escola Superior de Agricultura “Luiz de Queiroz”, Departamento de Ciências Florestais, Laboratório de Ecologia, Manejo e Conservação da Fauna Silvestre – Av. Pádua Dias, 11, Piracicaba, SP, 13418-900, Brasil.

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3088-4524>

eduardoalexandrino@hotmail.com

The term 'citizen science' is now well-established among Brazilian ornithologists¹, including those just starting their careers. For many of them, the term probably evokes an instant association with platforms like eBird and WikiAves, both of which are based on the free sharing of ornithological records (e.g., species lists, photographs, sound files) made by the public from various locations and time periods. Even if it is possible to find ornithologists who are "non-users" of these platforms, they have probably read some scientific publication that utilized data from these platforms. In fact, Brazilian ornithology has increased in the last 10 years thanks to the massive public contribution to eBird and WikiAves. Citing some examples, we have improved our understanding of the migratory movements of some species (Schubert et al. 2019, DeGroot et al. 2021, Lopes and Schunck 2022) and expanded our knowledge about the behaviors and natural history of many others (Turella et al. 2023). We have also broadened the geographic and temporal information about areas of occurrence of Brazilian species (Klemann-Junior et al. 2017) and we have provided more robust foundations for planning a conservation agenda (<https://www.gov.br/icmbio/pt-br/assuntos/biodiversidade/pan/pan-aves-da-mata-atlantica>).

However, if eBird and WikiAves sound like a synonym of 'citizen science' to many Brazilian ornithologists, this indicates a limited understanding of the subject remains among this community, which hinders the growth of this scientific approach in the country. Thus, in this manuscript, I raise points that are still rarely discussed about citizen science among Brazilians and provoke a reflection on the pros and cons for our future. This reflection is the result of eight years of observing citizen science being applied in Brazil and my recent experience at the Cornell Lab of Ornithology, where citizen science is extensively practiced and discussed. Three topics guide my reflection – engagement, learning, and public awareness; governance and sustainability of citizen science initiatives; and allocation of funding and future resources. The idea is not to break the optimism and deny the benefits already accomplished, but to initiate discussions that could

¹ Consider anyone who is enthusiastic about Brazilian birds and produces knowledge based on scientific methodology, whether he/she is paid for this or not, regardless of their expertise.

identify ways to enhance and diversify this scientific approach in Brazilian ornithology in the long term.

First, I brought a brief outline of what citizen science is and its origins (Box A). Based on this, I invite you to engage with the reflections presented in this manuscript.

Box A - Citizen science is way more complex

In general terms, citizen science involves engaging the public with various scientific topics and the acquisition of scientific knowledge. Since the term emerged within different disciplines in the mid-1990s, it remains challenging to find a single definition for it. Alan Irwin (1995), a social scientist, used the term to explain that science and the decisions arising from it should include citizens at different stages of the knowledge-building process, i.e., science should be done for and with citizens and should not be distanced from society. On the other hand, Rick Bonney (1996), an ornithologist, considered 'citizen science' as the process by which formal researchers² ask citizens to help them collect data in a scientific investigation, and in return, the citizens learn something. After years of discussions, there is now a consensus that the definition of citizen science is context-dependent (Haklay et al. 2021a). In Brazil, the Brazilian Network of Citizen Science (RBCC) adopts a definition that encompasses the ideas of Irwin and Bonney (see RBCC 2024) to support a variety of partnerships between science and Brazilian society.

Ornithological projects or initiatives generally consider citizen science as "the participation of non-professionals in genuine scientific investigations" (e.g., Miller-Rushing et al. 2012, Shirk et al. 2012), i.e., an approach aligned with Booney (1996). According to the definitions proposed by Bonney et al. (2009) and Shirk et al. (2012), the form of citizen participation can vary in intensity, frequency, and at different levels of the scientific project. For example, when citizens only collect data, they are acting at the contributory level, whether in an online environment or in person (e.g., iNaturalist, eBird, and WikiAves). At higher levels of involvement, such as collaboration, citizens also participate in the design of the study, data analysis, and dissemination of the results. Finally, when citizens participate in all stages of scientific research, such as formulating the study question, designing the study, collecting and analyzing data, disseminating results, and making decisions, they are acting at the co-created level. Given the vast scope of citizen science, it is recommended to look at different ways to categorize the levels of citizen participation (see Ceccaroni et al. 2017, Haklay et al. 2021a, and Haklay et al. 2021b).

Brazilian birdwatchers contribute to eBird and WikiAves. Isn't that enough to help ornithology?

The answer to the question is 'yes,' but the scope of public participation in Brazilian ornithology can still be expanded. It is undeniable that more birdwatchers have emerged in Brazil thanks to platforms like eBird and WikiAves (Alexandrino et al. 2018). Analyzing WikiAves

² This manuscript considers 'formal researchers' as professionals who are paid to carry out scientific research.

specifically, after 15 years of its existence, it is possible to see the mutual benefit between birdwatching and Brazilian science, where the number of users and ornithological records uploaded to the platform positively correlates with the number of scientific texts published over the last few years (Figure 1). The critical point is that most ornithological studies being conducted in the country based on citizen science follow an approach where citizens are only collecting data for eBird and WikiAves, and to a lesser extent for iNaturalist, a platform with similar functions (i.e., *contributory* level, Albagli and Rocha 2021). Two main reasons for this scenario are: The relative ease of using data deposited on these platforms compared to other steps that must be carried out in local projects (i.e. raising funds, understanding the needs and preferences of the target audience, engaging them, training them, and maintaining their involvement throughout the project), and the difficulty of obtaining citizen participation beyond data collection (i.e., carrying out data analysis, disseminating results, etc.; Alexandrino et al. in press³).

Figure 1. Number of academic papers (e.g., articles, books, book chapters, dissertations, theses, etc.) published between 2009 and 2019 that used WikiAves and their relationship with the number of registered users on the platform (top graph) and bird records uploaded (photos and sounds) during the same period (bottom graph). The academic publications were obtained through a search on Google Scholar between January 3 and March 3, 2024, using the keyword 'WikiAves'. In total, 960 records were analyzed. These are preliminary data from an ongoing project⁴.

³ Alexandrino ER, Ghilardi-Lopes NP, Ferraz KMPMB. 2024. Reflexões sobre o cenário acadêmico brasileiro para promover ciência cidadã em pesquisas ecológicas e de conservação ambiental. *Estudos Avançados*. Article accepted.

⁴ Project: 'Benefits and challenges of citizen science: examples from US to guide initiatives in Brazil' (FAPESP 2023/10137-5).

Although the progression of WikiAves numbers and the science produced suggests a purely positive scenario for Brazilian society and academia, the *modus operandi* and sustainability of this 'ornithology-society' model based on large online platforms for sharing ornithological records (Figure 2) have potential critical points, as discussed below.

Figure 2. (A) Model of interconnection between academy and society driven by large citizen science online platforms. Each event at the edge of this pentagonal model leads to the occurrence of the following events (arrows). (B) When this model is the only one practiced over the years by formal scientists and citizens, the perception that this is the only form of citizen science is heightened. Although this is an empirical model, it is supported by the numbers presented in Figure 1 and by the fact that in Brazil, there is a low occurrence of projects that engage birdwatchers at different levels of participation.

1) *Do large platforms create barriers to other citizen science practices?* Within the theoretical discussions of citizen science, some authors have questioned the execution and popularization of projects that limit citizens to data collection through large online platforms (Figure 2; Sauermann and Franzoni 2015, Parrish et al. 2019, Blacker et al. 2021, Fontúrbel 2023, Queiroz-Souza et al. 2023). For example, there is concern that such popularization could compromise the development of public policies and institutional programs that encourage projects above the contributory level and prioritize environmental issues at local scales (Queiroz-Souza et al. 2023, Mady et al. 2023). Additionally, it may transmit the wrong message to formal researchers that citizens are free labor without the need for appropriate reward or recognition (Guerrini et al. 2018, Blacker et al. 2021, Fontúrbel 2023). The competitive spirit promoted by the platforms among users (e.g., top 100, indication of the first user to find a species, etc.) can compromise the user's perception of the importance of data for science. At this point, there are cases of citizens

participating with the interest of only generating data quantity instead of data with high quality for science (e.g., Sauermann and Franzoni 2015, Parrish et al. 2019).

There is also concern that the popularization of the mentioned platforms could restrict society's understanding of citizen science, as the public might come to interpret that their online ornithological records are enough for science (e.g., Sauermann and Franzoni 2015, Parrish et al. 2019). Once this scenario is established, it becomes difficult to engage birdwatchers in ornithological projects operating at higher levels of citizen science or requiring specific bird data. This was experienced by the “Did I see a banded bird!?” (original name in Portuguese - “*Eu vi uma ave usando pulseiras!?*”), a Brazilian project that promotes the monitoring of banded birds on a local scale; see www.avesusandopulseiras.com.br). Throughout its different phases, the project faced difficulties in recruiting birdwatchers and had to break the natural behavior of the participants to send records of banded birds directly to eBird or WikiAves instead of following the project's participation protocol (Alexandrino et al., in press⁵).

On the other hand, it is important to highlight that not all participants of large contributory initiatives will be the best audience for specific projects that operate locally or practice other levels of citizen science, an argument I've heard within the Cornell Lab of Ornithology. For example, several participants in two of the institution's citizen science projects, Project FeederWatch (which monitors birds at feeders) and NestWatch (which monitors birds in nests), are not regular eBird users. I observed something similar when the “Did I see a banded bird!?” project monitored the brief life of a Red-legged Seriema chick born in an urban environment (“Luiz de Queiroz” university campus in Piracicaba/SP), with the participation of hundreds of non-birdwatchers unaware of major citizen science platforms (Alexandrino et al. 2019b, Alexandrino 2023). I also observed the same situation years ago in the ‘Bromélias’ and ‘Cantoria de Quintal’ projects, both of which started monitoring amphibians with the rural population of the Central Mountainous Region of Espírito Santo state (Lacerda et al. 2023, Zocca and Lima 2023).

2) *Does the governance and management of the platforms make them sustainable in the long term?* Let's examine how eBird and WikiAves are structured. eBird was launched in 2002 within the Cornell Lab of Ornithology, in the United States, with the aim of carrying out citizen science. Although it started with a small team of fewer than 10 members, as the geographical scope of the project expanded and it became connected to other scientific projects within and outside the institution (e.g., National Audubon Society and Macaulay Library), a much larger and diverse team now works for it. Each professional is hired to perform specific functions on the platform (e.g., programmers, resource managers, content creators for the site, researchers, etc.). The financial resources to maintain it come from the previously mentioned Lab, which has a specific sector for

⁵ Alexandrino ER, Alcantara MC, Ermenegildo H, Campos LKN, Costa GI, Bessi TC, Gobbi A S, Ferraz KMPMB. 2024. Como a curiosidade humana norteou um projeto de ciência cidadã que monitora aves anilhadas? Lições aos futuros projetos brasileiros. Boletim do Museu de Biologia Professor Mello Leitão. Special issue 'Citizen Science for the Conservation and Sustainability of the Atlantic Forest' (Article accepted).

fundraising, managing resources, and managing personnel (e.g., hiring, payments, etc.). It is worth mentioning that approximately 70% of the lab's funding comes from donations from civil society, including companies and enthusiastic citizens⁶. The lab invests in continuous improvements to eBird, as well as a massive amount of scientific communication material (e.g., All About Birds, BirdCams, Living Birds, etc.). These are characteristics that together make eBird a robust and consolidated platform, maintaining high chances of its longevity and continuous engagement of new users. The situation is very different with WikiAves. It was created in December 2008 with the intention of being a channel to gradually gather information about Brazilian birds, acting as an encyclopedia of Brazil's birds (a definition that accompanies its name). Initially, the photographs and sounds of birds submitted by users were intended to illustrate the characteristics of the species. However, because the format of submitting photos and sounds required users to indicate the municipality and date where the bird was recorded, the site began to show the geographical and temporal extent of the species, something that made it popular among citizens and extremely useful to Brazilian academics. Nowadays, the site is widely considered to be a "citizen science platform" and is defined as such by academics and non-academics. The platform was created using the personal resources of its creator, Reinaldo Guedes, and according to him, without help from others. Since its creation, it has mainly been maintained through voluntary donations from its users and occasional partnerships. Only once, 12 years ago, the platform received a small grant from the Boticário Foundation. There are no employees or a monthly paid team, and those who raise the funds and make the decisions are the same people who perform technical functions to keep everything in order (i.e., Reinaldo and a few volunteers). This means that those who manage the platform do not always find enough time to keep up with the demands and ideas for improvement suggested by the many users. Even with so many limitations, its simple and low-cost administration has invested in occasional innovations, such as the artificial intelligence program that suggests the identification of species contained in the submitted photographs, launched in May 2023.

Although both platforms accumulate incredible ornithological records that are extremely important to Brazilian ornithology, the difference in their management is enormous. Since 2021, when more Brazilians began discussing citizen science (i.e., with the creation of the Brazilian Citizen Science Network), I have observed more professionals who rely on WikiAves (e.g., academics and birdwatching guides) raising doubts about what might happen to the platform if its maintainer is no longer able to work on it. The most interesting detail when this topic arises among non-academics is the belief that WikiAves should have governance similar to eBird, and it is common to hear arguments like, "Wow! Then WikiAves needs to be within a research institution in Brazil." After years in the Brazilian academic world, I now realize that such a decision would

⁶ Data from 2023, in the annual report of the Cornell Lab of Ornithology. <https://www.birds.cornell.edu/home/annual-report/>. For many Brazilians who are not familiar with this institution, its name might suggest a simple space within a university, something commonly found in Brazil. However, this "laboratory" has autonomy and little dependence on Cornell University, being a building of approximately 5000 square meters that houses six research centers and more than 280 employees.

be very risky, as it does not seem feasible to replicate eBird's governance model for WikiAves if it were within a Brazilian public institution. Brazilian institutions that research topics aligned with WikiAves (e.g., ecology and ornithology) are maintained almost entirely by public funds, such as universities and research institutions. The management style and rules for using resources within these institutions, methods of hiring staff, contracting external services and payment, image use policy, and other administrative factors are completely different from those experienced by eBird, as well as from what WikiAves currently experiences. It is worth mentioning that donations of extremely high figures from civil society are not a common research funding model in Brazil, and when they do occur, the path that the resource takes within a public institution can be long and bureaucratic.

Sometimes I wonder if an alternative for WikiAves would be to follow in the footsteps of iNaturalist. This platform was created in 2008 as a master's project by two students at the University of California, Berkeley's School of Information. Over the years it has expanded through partnerships; in 2014 the platform began to be co-managed by the California Academy of Sciences, and in 2017 it began to be jointly managed by the National Geographic Society. For example, in 2021, eight people were employed by the platform, along with service providers⁷ paid with funds from research grants and donations. After being mainly based in American institutions, in 2023, it gained the status of a 'non-profit organization' (*501c3 non-profit organization*, in U.S. terms. Ironically, this is the same status as the Cornell Lab of Ornithology, even though it is connected to Cornell University). This current status facilitates autonomy in raising and using funds. In Brazil, similar categories are Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) or Civil Society Organizations of Public Interest (OSCIP), which is something the administrators of WikiAves could consider.

Although we can suggest ways to make WikiAves more secure, another point needs to be considered - there are diverse opinions among its thousands of users, and any intention to attach the platform to an institution would certainly generate both positive and negative feedback for its creator, who would, in turn, need to be willing to venture into this new and possibly stressful endeavor. As Reinaldo Guedes reports, I have also heard statements from birdwatchers and photographers who are extremely keen on WikiAves saying they would not like to see their photos managed by a Brazilian or foreign institution (i.e., if Cornell would offer help), and if that happened, they would possibly withdraw their records from the platform. I have noticed that there are users who feel a certain comfort in having their records on an independent and non-institutionalized Brazilian platform for the following reasons: Their records remain "neutral" to any supposed partisan position that a public institution might have. This may seem absurd at first, but the political polarization experienced in Brazil in recent years ('left vs. right') has indeed been observed among those who generate valuable ornithological records. In some way, this polarization has affected the perception of some Brazilians about the credibility of research

⁷ Information based on Carie Stezer's report during the 1st Workshop of the Brazilian Citizen Science Network (<https://youtu.be/OVwedCdtEEY?si=hDB-RVpUBIcW9l0>) and on the platform's website (<https://www.inaturalist.org/pages/about>).

institutions supported by the public authorities, as they believe that science has ceased to be neutral; There is a certain sense of pride and nationalism among many WikiAves users, creating a misguided view that accepting support from a foreign institution would mean "giving away" valuable data for free to the "colonizer". Although these sentiments have been openly declared by a minority, we cannot deny that today we are bombarded by *Fake News* that quickly creates trends among a less informed audience. Any removal of data from the platforms, generated by feelings of dissatisfaction, would result in a significant negative impact on science, and this is the crucial point of this reflection.

3) *Does the public learn anything by using the major platforms?* When citizens limit their participation in science to uploading records to platforms, the scientific knowledge produced by academics that used those records will only return to the citizens if extensive scientific communication is published in accessible language. Most platform users do not read academic articles. In the case of eBird, other sectors of the Cornell Lab of Ornithology already handle the task of scientific communication. However, for WikiAves, the study authors themselves are responsible for this task. Many Brazilians lack support from their academic institutions to publish their studies in popular formats, and on their own, many cannot dedicate time to this. From a negative perspective, failing to return knowledge to the population could jeopardize the learning and awareness of citizens who, consequently, might also have their scientific and environmental citizenship compromised (i.e., the behavior of proposing environmental solutions or demanding action from authorities and decision-makers based on the learning obtained from participating in a citizen science project; Ceccaroni et al. 2017, Jørgensen and Jørgensen 2021). However, this negative view of major platforms can be overturned. We see reports from professionals across Brazil arguing that even if some platform users are only interested in competing with each other or have no interest in being part of a scientific investigation, these platforms can still generate environmental awareness in a much larger group of people. This is due to the environment of discussions these platforms may create, as well as the quality of visual and textual materials that captivate users to navigate through them. These reports support similar arguments already highlighted in academic texts (e.g., Trumbull et al. 2000, Bonney et al. 2009, Silva and Nery 2019, Adler et al. 2020).

Future Funding – Allocating to Large or Small Initiatives?

In the past five years, programs to incentivize academic projects based on citizen science have become more common in Brazil⁸. Similarly, since 2021, public policies to encourage the implementation of this science have been considered and discussed (Jorge et al. 2022, Queiroz-

⁸ In recent years, specific public calls in Brazil to support citizen science initiatives and develop this field have been observed, for example, at University of Sao Paulo - Portaria Pró-Reitoria de Pesquisa da USP n.743 of December 9, 2019; at National Institute of the Atlantic Forest - INMA Edital 01/2019 - Programa de Capacitação Institucional do Instituto Nacional da Mata Atlântica; approval of the National Institute of Citizen Science (INCT-CC) in December 2023, see <https://www.gov.br/ibict/pt-br/central-de-conteudos/noticias/2023/dezembro/instituto-nacional-de-ciencia-cidada-incc-e-aprovado-em-chamada-do-cnpq>.

Souza et al. 2023, <https://revistapesquisa.fapesp.br/o-avanco-da-ciencia-cidada/>). However, as citizen science is still relatively untested in the country, there is little support regarding which project formats and respective governance structures are most effective in each research context. When thinking about the development of public policies to create funding lines for these initiatives, there is a recurring question among decision-makers - where should resources be invested when they become available and how can they be optimized? Should we support local projects, encourage the creation of new large platforms, or only strengthen the already established platforms? Of course, to provide precise answers to these questions, a much more extensive manuscript would be necessary. Therefore, I urge other ornithologists in Brazil to reflect on this issue. However, here are a few points worth highlighting:

In the case of large platforms, it is crucial to remember that they deal with a diverse audience, requiring constant attention to societal trends. Appearance, usability, public recognition, feedback format, and display of results are essential to maintain the engagement of current and future audiences. If at any point society or formal scientists lose interest in the platform, it could suffer significant losses. Thus, having access to lines of funding increases the chances for large platforms to make improvements as needed by the public, making it possible to maintain them in the long term. Here it is worth remembering what happened with Taxeus (<https://www.taxeus.com.br/>), a site for sharing species lists across different taxa. Created by Brazilians in 2010, it initially had a considerable number of users (see Alexandrino et al. 2018). However, with the popularization of eBird in Brazil, birdwatchers stopped using it, as Taxeus did not have the appearance and functionalities at the same level. Because it was a non-institutionalized initiative and there was no incentive in the country to maintain this tool, in November 2021, its founders declared that they would no longer invest their time and money in the platform.

Small local initiatives are also dependent on funding at different stages of the project. In March 2021, at the 1st Workshop of the Brazilian Citizen Science Network, it was revealed that 104 small-scale projects declared that their main resources to run the project were 'project coordinator's own funds', 'coordinator's post-graduate student fellowship' and 'funds from research grants' (see <https://youtu.be/7M7FC3MrxI0> and Queiroz-Souza et al. 2023). This scenario reinforces that many citizen science projects in Brazil are being carried out on a low budget and struggle to keep everything running smoothly (i.e., recruiting, training, and engaging volunteers, obtaining high-quality data, achieving research goals, etc., see Alexandrino et al. 2019a, Alexandrino et al. in press⁵).

Although lines of funding for large and small citizen science initiatives in Brazil are important, I must highlight that without a proper evaluation of project performance, it will not be possible to optimize future resources that may emerge. Recently, Brazil has begun to follow the global trend of developing appropriate indicators to evaluate such projects (i.e., discussions driven

by institutional initiatives that transcend borders, such as the Open Government Partnership⁹), culminating in a useful document for Brazilian funding agencies (Jorge et al. 2022). In this case, there are two factors that meet the demands from academia and society – measuring scientific impacts (e.g., academic productions) and social impacts (e.g., public engagement, provided learning, scientific citizenship, access to data, etc.) achieved by each the projects. In this context, it is worth stressing that Brazil needs to highlight the impacts of current and already completed citizen science initiatives¹⁰, as such information serves as a reference point when formulating programs to encourage this scientific approach. Therefore, ending this manuscript, I invite coordinators of Brazilian citizen science projects, as well as academics interested in the subject, to make public the social and scientific impacts of different initiatives. There is still a lack of experience reports, leaving various citizen science enthusiasts without examples to follow or avoid.

I hope the brief reflections presented have created a feeling among Brazilian ornithologists that "we need to continue this discussion".

Acknowledgments

The points presented here are the result of my current postdoctoral project, partly conducted at the Laboratory of Ecology, Management, and Conservation of Wildlife (LEMaC/LCF/ESALQ-USP) and partly at the Cornell Lab of Ornithology (FAPESP Processes No. 2022/01242-7; 2023/10137-5).

The original paper in Portuguese is available here:

https://ararajuba.org.br/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/bol_sbo_v10n34_jun2024_22jul2024-1.pdf

References

- Adler FR, Green AM, Şekercioğlu ÇH. 2020. Citizen science in ecology: a place for humans in nature. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1469(1): 52-64.
- Albagli S, Rocha L. 2021. Ciência cidadã no Brasil: um estudo exploratório In: Borges MM e Casado ES. *Sob a lente da ciência aberta. Olhares de Portugal, Espanha e Brasil*. Imprensa da Universidade de Coimbra. pp. 489-511
- Alexandrino ER, Mendes RLS, Ferraz KMPMB, Couto HTZ. 2018. Regiões paulistas carentes de registros ornitológicos feitos por cidadãos cientistas. *Atualidades Ornitológicas* 201: 33–39.

⁹ The OGP's main objective is to globally promote and encourage government practices related to the principles of transparency, social participation, accountability, and innovation. In general terms, it seeks a new model of political-administrative interaction that prioritizes citizens in public policies and establishes specific values and principles as strategies for the design, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation of public policies and administrative modernization processes. The OGP includes 76 signatory countries, including Brazil, and is made up of internal and external members from the participating governments.

¹⁰ In my current postdoctoral research, I am evaluating the scientific and social impacts generated by WikiAves and comparing its performance with citizen science projects conducted by the Cornell Lab of Ornithology that operate on a national scale, such as Project FeederWatch. Although several ornithologists and ecologists have already published studies using data from WikiAves (Figure 1), I aim to discover whether this platform has been used in educational activities and how frequently. If you identify as an educator, or know someone who does, I invite you to a quick interview at this link: https://bit.ly/educadores_usando_wikiaves.

- Alexandrino ER, Navarro AB, Paulete VF, Camolesi M, Lima VGR, Green A, Conto T, Ferraz KMPMB, Sekercioglu CH, Couto HTZ. 2019a. Challenges in Engaging Birdwatchers in Bird Monitoring in a Forest Patch: Lessons for Future Citizen Science Projects in Agricultural Landscapes. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 4(1): 4.
- Alexandrino ER, Bogoni JA, Navarro AB, Bovo AAA, Gonçalves RM, Charters JD, Domini JA, Ferraz KMPMB. 2019b. Large Terrestrial Bird Adapting Behavior in an Urbanized Zone. *Animals* 9(6): 351.
- Alexandrino ER, Silva GA, Corbo MC, Demuner BA, Szabo JK. 2022. Urban southern house wren (*Troglodytes aedon musculus*) nesting in apparently unsuitable human-made structures: Is it worth it. *Ornitología Neotropical*, 33, 44-52. <https://doi.org/10.58843/ornneo.v33i1.879>
- Alexandrino ER, 2023. Investigando aves que vivem próximas de nós. In: GHILARDI-LOPES, N.P.; LIMA, I.M.S. (Eds) Série Ciência Cidadã na Mata Atlântica. Santa Teresa/ES: Instituto Nacional da Mata Atlântica. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11237798>
- Blacker S, Kimura AH, Kinchy A. 2021. When citizen science is public relations. *Social studies of science*, 51(5), 780-796.
- Bonney R.1996. Citizen science: A Lab Tradition. *Living Bird* 15: 7–15.
- Bonney R, Ballard H, Jordan R, McCallie E, Phillips T, Shirk J, Wilderman CC. 2000. Public Participation in Scientific Research: Defining the Field and Assessing Its Potential for Informal Science Education. A CAISE Inquiry Group Report. Washington, D.C.: Center for Advancement of Informal Science Education (CAISE).
- Ceccaroni L, Bowser A, Brenton P. 2017. Civic Education and Citizen Science: Definitions, Categories, Knowledge Representation. In L. Ceccaroni, & J. Piera (Eds.), *Analyzing the Role of Citizen Science in Modern Research* (pp. 1-23). Hershey, PA: IGI Global. doi:10.4018/978-1-5225-0962-2.ch001
- Haklay MM, Dörler D, Heigl F, Manzoni M, Hecker S, Vohland K. 2021a. What Is Citizen Science? The Challenges of Definition. In: Vohland K, Land-Zandstra A, Ceccaroni L, Lemmens R, Perelló J, Ponti M, Samson R, Wagenknecht K (Eds). *The Science of Citizen Science*. Springer: Switzerland. pp.13-34.
- Haklay M, Fraisl D, Tzovaras BG, Hecker S, Gold M, Hager G, Ceccaroni L, Kieslinger B, Wehn U, Woods S, Nold C, Balázs B, Mazzonetto M, Rufenacht S, Shanley LA, Wagenknecht K, Motion A, Sforzi A, Riemenschneider D, Dorler D, Heigl F, Schaefer T, Lindner A, Weißpflug M, Ma M, Vohland K. 2021b. Contours of citizen science: a vignette study. *Royal Society Open Science*, 8(8): 202108.
- DeGroot LW, Hingst-Zaher E, Moreira-Lima L, Whitacre JV, Snyder JB, Wenzel JW. 2021. Citizen science data reveals the cryptic migration of the Common Potoo *Nyctibius griseus* in Brazil. *Ibis*, 163(2): 380-389.
- Fontúrbel FE. 2023. Predatory Citizen Science? *Bulletin of the Ecological Society of America*. 104(3):e02075. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bes2.2075>
- Guerrini CJ, Majumder MA, Lewellyn MJ, Mcguire ML. 2018. Citizen science, public policy. *Science*, 361,134-136. DOI:10.1126/science.aar8379
- Irwin A. 1995. *Citizen science: A Study of People, Expertise, and Sustainable Development*. London and New York: Routledge.
- Jorge VA, Albagli S, Rocha L, Sena P, Braga T, Corrêa MFMM. 2022. Indicadores de Avaliação e Apoio à Ciência Cidadã, Arca Dados, v2. <https://doi.org/10.35078/DP2DGZ>
- Jørgensen FA, Jørgensen D. 2021. Citizen science for environmental citizenship. *Conservation Biology*, 35(4): 1344.
- Klemann-Junior L, Villegas Vallejos MA, Scherer-Neto P, Vitule JRS. 2017. Traditional scientific data vs. uncoordinated citizen science effort: A review of the current status and comparison of data on avifauna in Southern Brazil. *PLoS ONE* 12(12): e0188819. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0188819>
- Lacerda JVA, Santos AZ, Lima IMS. 2023. Coaxos de ciência e educação. In: GHILARDI-LOPES, N.P.; LIMA, I.M.S. (Eds) Série Ciência Cidadã na Mata Atlântica. Santa Teresa/ES: Instituto Nacional da Mata Atlântica. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11237658>
- Mady RP, Phillips TB, Bonter DN, Quimby C, Borland J, Eldermire C, Walters BT, Parry SA, Chu M. 2023. Engagement in the Data Collection Phase of the Scientific Process is Key for Enhancing Learning Gains. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 8(1): 14. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.594>
- Miller-Rushing A, Primack R, Bonney R. 2012. The history of public participation in ecological research. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment* 10(6): 285-290.

- Parrish JK, Jones T, Burgess HK, He Y, Fortson L, Cavalier D. 2019. Hoping for optimality or designing for inclusion: Persistence, learning, and the social network of citizen science. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 116(6): 1894-1901.
- Queiroz-Souza C, Viana B, Ghilardi-Lopes N, Kawabe L, Alexandrino E, França J, Koffler S, Saraiva AM & Loula A. 2023. Opportunities and Barriers for Citizen Science Growth in Brazil: Reflections from the First Workshop of the Brazilian Citizen Science Network. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 8(1),13. <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.521>
- Sauermann H, Franzoni C. 2015. Crowd science user contribution patterns and their implications. *Proceedings of the national academy of sciences*, 112(3): 679-684.
- Silva JAD, Nery ASD. 2019. Uma proposta de uso da plataforma Wiki Aves como um facilitador na aprendizagem de temas ambientais relacionados à ornitologia. *Revista Thema*, 16(3), 607–616. <https://doi.org/10.15536/thema.V16.2019.607-616.1344>
- Schubert SC, Manica LT, Guaraldo AC. 2019. Revealing the potential of a huge citizen-science platform to study bird migration, *Emu - Austral Ornithology* 119(4): 364-373.
- Shirk JL, Ballard HL, Wilderman CC, Phillips T, Wiggins A, Jordan R, McCallie E, Minarchek M, Lewenstein BV, Krasny ME, Bonney R. 2012. Public participation in scientific research: a framework for deliberate design. *Ecology and Society*, 17(2):29.
- Trumbull DJ, Bonney R, Bascom D, Cabral A. 2000. Thinking scientifically during participation in a citizen-science project. *Science education*, 84(2), 265-275.